

Methods for Removal of Cyanide and Phenol in the Effluent of Coke Oven and By-Product Plant

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The effluent of coke oven and by-product plant of Rourkela steel mill contains, amongst other, certain amount of cyanide and phenol. The average of ten estimated values of cyanide and phenol noted on different dates are about 18.79 mg/litre and 66.92 mg/litre of effluent, respectively. Several methods have been used to remove cyanide and phenol from this effluent and the residual amounts estimated. Economic aspects of the methods have been discussed.

WASTE water emanating from different factories containing suspended solids, lubricants and several toxic substances causes pollution of water and in one way or the other adversely affect the environment. Such effluent from coke oven and by-product plants of integrated steel mills, if discharged into a stream without any treatment, creates environmental problem. Cyanide and phenol being harmful substances can disturb the ecology of the receiving stream and hence should be removed from the effluent economically. A close examination of the literature reveals that though considerable amount of work^{1,2} has been done on this problem, very few processes have been studied thoroughly. In the present work attempts have been made to estimate cyanide and phenol present in the effluent of coke oven and by-product plant of Rourkela steel mill. Further, several methods have been tried to remove cyanide and phenol from the effluent. The residual amounts of the two have also been estimated and the best methods for effluent treatment have been suggested.

Experimental

The effluent samples were collected from the coke oven and by-product plant on different dates. The amount of simple cyanide present in it was determined by titrating against 0.1 N AgNO₃ solution, after removal of sulphide with 10% Pb(NO₃)₂ and distilling to sodium hydroxide solution. *p*-Dimethylaminobenzal rhodanine was used as indicator which changes the colour from yellow to pink at the end point. The quantity of total cyanide in the effluent was estimated by the method of Patricia *et al*³. The quantity of phenol present was determined by standard procedure³, in the distillate obtained after removal of NH₃ and sulphides from the effluent by boiling with caustic alkali and PbCO₃, successively. All the chemicals used were of reagent grade.

Removal of cyanide :

The following methods were tried for the removal of cyanide from the effluent.

- (A) 20 ml freshly prepared FeSO₄ solution of varying concentration was added to 100 ml effluent at pH > 11 with stirring. The pH was maintained by addition of required amount of sodium hydroxide. The precipitate was filtered and the residual cyanide was estimated in the filtrate.
- (B) 100 ml effluent was treated with 20 ml FeCl₃ solution of varying concentration at a pH > 11 with stirring. It was then filtered and the filtrate was analysed for residual cyanide.
- (C) In order to remove cyanide 100 ml effluent was mixed with 10% MgSO₄.7H₂O (10 ml) and then treated with 37% HCHO (10 ml) and 35% H₂O₂ (30 ml). The pH was adjusted between 10-12 and the mixture heated for 15 min at 60-80°. The residual amount of cyanide was estimated.
- (D) Maintaining the pH above 11, the effluent (100 ml) was treated with 20 ml 20% FeSO₄ solution. The precipitate formed was filtered and the filtrate was treated with a small quantity of sodium hypochlorite (10 ml, 0.1 M) and analysed for the residual cyanide content.

Removal of phenol :

The following methods were tried for the removal of phenol from the effluent.

- (E) 25 ml effluent was shaken vigorously with different volumes of toluene separately for ~ 20 min in a separating funnel and allowed to stand for 0.5 hr. The aqueous layer was separated quantitatively with washings and estimated for residual phenol.
- (F) The above process was also followed using benzene in place of toluene.
- (G) 25 ml effluent was treated with different quantity of lime. The reaction mixture was warmed upto 60° with stirring and filtered. The residual quantity of phenol was estimated in the filtrate.

(H) The effluent was allowed to pass through a column containing activated granulated charcoal of volume 42.239 cm³. The rate of addition of the sample was adjusted to 0.3 ml per minute. The residual phenol was estimated. This column of charcoal was used over and over again for each 25 ml fresh sample to have an idea about the efficiency of charcoal absorption method.

Results and Discussion

The effluent originating from the coke oven and by-product plant under study contains a number of toxic chemicals. The typical concentrations of these are : free ammonia ≥ 400 mg/l, sulphide ≤ 700 mg/l, thiocyanate = 100 to 300 mg/l, phenol = 50 to 150 mg/l, cyanide = 10 to 50 mg/l. Though all these pollutants can affect the ecology of the waste-receiving water course, phenol and cyanide are considered to be the most objectionable pollutants.

The effluent contains cyanide both in free and complexed form, as ferro- and ferricyanides. For the determination of free cyanide argentometric method has been chosen using an adsorption indicator. The analysis for total cyanide was done after breaking the complex cyanide by addition of MgCl₂ as indicated by equation (1),

M stands for a monovalent metal ion.

As all silver salts except the sulphides are readily soluble in excess of a solution of alkali cyanides, the presence of chloride does not interfere in the above method. The sulphide was removed prior to argentometric estimation by treatment with lead nitrate and cadmium carbonate, respectively in the two methods of estimation discussed above. The results of cyanide content, simple, complex and total, are shown in Table 1. For the estimation of phenol

TABLE 1—QUANTITY OF CYANIDE AND PHENOL PRESENT IN THE EFFLUENT ON DIFFERENT DATES

Total cyanide mg/litre	Simple cyanides mg/litre	Complex cyanides mg/litre (by difference)	Total phenol mg/litre
20.52	17.28	3.24	75.12
19.44	16.20	3.24	52.58
13.50	9.72	3.78	60.09
17.25	13.57	3.68	103.91
11.80	8.10	3.70	126.45
20.52	16.20	4.32	91.39

in the effluent, the ammonia and sulphide impurities present were removed by boiling with caustic alkali and by subsequent treatment with lead carbonate and filtration. The filtrate containing phenol was brominated using an excess of standard solution of bromate-bromide, followed by iodometric estimation. It is evident from the results

(Table 1) that the amount of complex cyanide does not vary much in the effluent from day to day, whereas the total cyanide as well as phenol content varies. This happens because all the units of the coke oven and by-product plant are not under operation always.

TABLE 2—REMOVAL OF CYANIDE BY METHOD 'A' FROM 100 ml EFFLUENT BY 20 ml FeSO₄ SOLUTION OF VARYING CONCENTRATION

Total cyanide present mg/litre	5% FeSO ₄		10% FeSO ₄		20% FeSO ₄	
	Residual mg/litre	% Removed	Residual mg/litre	% Removed	Residual mg/litre	% Removed
22.68	4.86	78.57	4.32	80.95	3.24	85.71
30.24	7.56	75.00	4.86	83.92	3.78	87.50
16.20	4.86	70.00	3.24	80.00	2.16	86.66
13.50	3.78	72.00	2.70	80.00	1.62	88.00
28.08	8.10	71.15	5.94	78.84	3.24	88.46
15.12	4.86	67.85	3.24	78.57	1.62	89.28

For the removal of cyanide from the effluent, four different methods (A, B, C and D) as mentioned under experimental were tried and the results are computed in Tables 2, 3 and 4. The pH of the effluent varies from 9.2 to 9.6. The required pH for

TABLE 3—REMOVAL OF CYANIDE BY METHOD 'C' FROM 100 ml EFFLUENT BY USING HCHO AND H₂O₂

Total cyanide present mg/litre	Residual cyanide mg/litre	% Removed
19.44	1.08	94.85
21.60	1.62	92.50
20.52	1.08	94.74
17.28	1.62	90.62
16.20	1.08	93.33

TABLE 4—REMOVAL OF CYANIDE BY METHOD 'D' FROM 100 ml EFFLUENT

Total cyanide present mg/litre	Residual cyanide mg/litre	% Removed
15.12	0.54	96.43
21.60	1.62	92.50
18.90	0.54	97.14
20.52	1.08	94.73
21.06	1.08	94.87

effective removal of cyanide by the above methods should be ≥ 11. So, the effluent is rendered alkaline by addition of pellets of sodium hydroxide. The resulting solution on treatment with ferrous sulphate through a series of reactions gives soluble ferrocyanides, which forms a blue precipitate of complex cyanide by the action of ferric ion generated by atmospheric oxidation and is separated by filtration (method A). On increasing the concentration of FeSO₄, the percentage removal of cyanide increased (Table 2). More than 85% removal was achieved by using 20 ml 20% FeSO₄ solution per 100 ml effluent and that is the optimum concentration. Addition of FeSO₄ beyond this concentration was found ineffective.

In a similar manner the effluent was treated with varying concentration of FeCl₃ (method B). Due to the presence of sulphide ions in the effluent some amount of Fe(III) is reduced to Fe(II) and the blue precipitate of complex cyanide formed by the same mechanism as above was separated by filtration. The results were compared with those of method (A) and no significant difference in the percentage removal of cyanide was marked.

The treatment suggested in method (C) involves the breaking of the complex cyanide by MgSO₄ into simple cyanides. The total simple cyanide is then oxidised to CO₂ and N₂ perhaps by performic acid formed by the action of HCHO and H₂O₂. The percentage removal is ≥ 90% (Table 3). By application of method (D) more than 95% of cyanide has been removed (Table 4). Here, the major amount of cyanide gets eliminated by treatment with FeSO₄ and the rest is oxidised to CO₂ and N₂ by hypochlorite ion. The stoichiometric equations for oxidation of cyanide in method (C) and (D) are given below by equations (2) and (3), respectively.

Several techniques have been developed⁶ for the removal and recovery of phenol from the effluent by liquid extraction method as it is a valuable chemical. In our method (E) and (F) toluene and benzene have been used as solvents respectively and these solvents are immiscible with the effluent. These solvents dissolve phenol present in the effluent and the organic solvent layer is separated. The extracted phenol can be recovered where it is economical. It is found that when the ratio of effluent to toluene is 10 : 3 (v/v), the removal is about 75% (Table 5). Further increase in the volume of toluene does not improve the partition. Similar results were obtained by method (F) using benzene as the

TABLE 5—REMOVAL OF PHENOL BY METHOD 'E' FROM 25 ml EFFLUENT

Total phenol present mg/litre	Effluent : Toluene (v/v)					
	10 : 2		10 : 3		10 : 4	
	Residual phenol mg/litre	% removed	Residual phenol mg/litre	% removed	Residual phenol mg/litre	% removed
51.33	22.53	56.10	12.52	75.60	12.52	75.60
60.09	28.79	52.08	13.77	77.18	13.77	77.18
75.12	40.06	46.67	20.03	73.35	18.78	75.00
91.39	42.56	53.43	22.53	75.34	22.53	75.34

solvent. In method (G) the effluent was mixed with lime above the room temperature. Here lime acts as a coagulant and removes phenol perhaps forming insoluble calcium phenolate. It is evident from the results that 4% lime treatment can be taken as the optimum condition by means of which about 75% of dephenolisation could be achieved (Table 6). It is also observed from the results in Table 7 that phenol

could be removed upto 75% from the effluent when passed through a column containing active charcoal (method 'H'). The active charcoal possesses remarkable capacity for adsorbing many substances. The column of the active charcoal could be used for dephenolisation to the same extent for several times.

TABLE 6—REMOVAL OF PHENOL BY METHOD 'G' FROM 25 ml EFFLUENT

Total phenol present mg/litre	2% lime treatment		4% lime treatment		6% lime treatment	
	Residual phenol mg/litre	% removed	Residual phenol mg/litre	% removed	Residual phenol mg/litre	% removed
76.37	36.30	52.46	18.78	75.40	18.78	75.40
45.07	21.28	52.78	10.01	77.79	10.01	77.79
60.09	26.29	56.24	13.77	77.18	13.77	77.18
51.33	22.53	56.10	12.52	75.60	11.89	76.81

TABLE 7—REMOVAL OF PHENOL BY METHOD 'H' FROM 25 ml EFFLUENT USING 21.0 cm CHARCOAL COLUMN CONTAINING 42.239 cm³ OF CHARCOAL

Total phenol present mg/litre	Residual phenol mg/litre	% removed
51.33	12.52	75.60
60.09	14.39	76.05
75.12	18.78	75.00
76.37	16.27	78.69
84.51	21.28	74.81

In the present study four methods have been adopted in each case for the removal of cyanide and phenol from the effluent in laboratory scale. Out of them, method 'D' for the removal of cyanide would be suitable for successful application in industry from the efficiency and economic points of view. One of the chemicals required for this method, i.e. ferrous sulphate is a by-product recovered from the pickling waste of the steel plant and available in plenty, which can be used for the purpose. With a small investment for other chemicals, this method can be applied for conditioning the effluent as the process does not involve much of engineering techniques. Other three methods would not be so suitable due to lack of efficiency and cost involved.

Among the four methods discussed for the removal of phenol, the most economic one is method 'H', which can be tried for industrial purpose. Here, adsorption technique has been applied for the removal. The adsorption involves the passage of the effluent through a fixed bed of active charcoal column. Other methods would not be so economical because of the cost of chemicals and technical devices involved. As the cyanide and phenol content in the effluent under study is not very significant, their recovery were not tried due to economical reasons.

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References

1. (a) D. W. SMITH, *J. Wat. Poll. Control. Fed.*, 1977, **49**, 1172; (b) J. B. PATRICIA, A. H. CAROL and C. K. DAVID, *J. Wat. Poll. Control. Fed.*, 1978, **50**, 234; (c) J. H. ROBERTSON and J. Y. LONGFIELD, *J. Wat. Poll. Control. Fed.*, 1979, **51**, 314.
2. (a) D. W. THOMAS and G. MARSHA, *J. Wat. Poll. Control. Fed.*, 1978, **50**, 543; (b) D. H. HELEN, *J. Wat. Poll. Control. Fed.*, 1978, **50**, 2771; (c) D. D. LEE, C. D. SCOTT and C. W. HANCHER, *J. Wat. Poll. Control. Fed.*, 1979, **51**, 974.
3. N. K. VISHNOI, "Advanced Practical Organic Chemistry", Vikas Publishing House Pvt. Ltd., Delhi, 1979, p. 432.
4. B. C. LAWES and O. B. MATHRE, *Chem. Abs.*, 1971, **75**, 143819h.
5. M. N. RAO and A. K. DATTA, "Waste Water Treatment", Oxford and IBH Publishing Co., Delhi, 1979, p. 293.